

Anatomical Variations of Kidney and Ureter Anomalies in Cadavers from the Nashik Region: A Comprehensive StudyVaishali S Anturlikar¹, Prashant M Moolya², Sushil Anturlikar³, Tushar Baheti⁴, Smita Avhad⁵, Jeetendra Singh⁶, Dhaval Patil⁷¹Associate Professor, Dept. of Anatomy, Government Medical College & Maharashtra Postgraduate Institute of Medical Education and Research, MUHS, Nashik, Maharashtra²Professor, Dept. of Anatomy, B.K.L. Walawalkar Rural Medical College, Sawarde³Associate Professor, Dept. of Medicine, Dr Vasanttrao Pawar Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Nashik⁴Associate Professor, Dept. of Pharmacology Government Medical College & Maharashtra Postgraduate Institute of Medical Education and Research, MUHS, Nashik, Maharashtra⁵Assistant Professor, Dept. of Pharmacology, Government Medical College & Maharashtra Postgraduate Institute of Medical Education and Research, MUHS, Nashik, Maharashtra⁶Professor and Head, Dept. of Pharmacology, Government Medical College & Maharashtra Postgraduate Institute of Medical Education and Research, MUHS, Nashik, Maharashtra⁷Assistant Professor, Dept. of Anatomy, Seth GS Medical College and KEMH, Mumbai

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

This study presents a detailed investigation into the prevalence, patterns, and unique characteristics of kidney and ureter anomalies among cadavers from the Nashik region of Maharashtra. Through meticulous cadaveric dissections, comprehensive anatomical observations, and thorough documentation, we unveil a spectrum of anomalies including polycystic kidney, lobulated kidney, and a variant of horseshoe kidney. Among 48 specimens, 24% exhibited renal and ureteric anomalies, with 18% showcasing kidney anomalies and 10% displaying double ureter. Noteworthy specimens were meticulously numbered, photographed, and analysed, revealing complex variations in renal position and ureteric architecture. This study contributes valuable insights into the local prevalence and characteristics of kidney and ureter anomalies, deepening our understanding of regional anatomical diversity.

Keywords: Renal anomalies, Horseshoe kidney, Double ureter, Polycystic kidney, Lobulated kidney, Kidney transplantation.

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Introduction

Kidney and ureter anomalies represent a fascinating and clinically significant area of study within the field of human anatomy. These variations, stemming from embryological, genetic, and environmental factors, have implications for both medical practitioners and researchers [1,2,3,4]. The understanding of regional prevalence, patterns, and characteristics of these anomalies contributes to better clinical diagnosis, surgical planning, and patient management [2]. The Nashik region of Maharashtra, with its unique demographic and genetic makeup, offers a distinctive setting to explore the intricacies of kidney and ureter anomalies.

In this original anatomical study, our primary objective is to uncover the prevalence, patterns, and potential contributing factors of kidney and ureter anomalies among cadavers from the Nashik region.

Through detailed dissections, anatomical observations, and thorough documentation, we endeavor to shed light on the regional diversity of these anomalies and their clinical implications.

Methods: A diverse and representative sample of 24 cadavers were used during the undergraduate teaching at SMBT Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Center, Dhamangaon, Nashik, Maharashtra, India, over a period of May 2019 to June 2020 during routine abdominal dissection. IEC approval was taken with proposal no. SMBT/IEC/2017/Project-77. Twenty-four cadavers comprising of 20 males and four females were dissected according to standard dissection technique given in Cunningham's practical manual [5]. The other viscera were removed and kidneys were exposed. Variations in kidney and ureter morphology and ureteric architecture were

documented. The specimens were numbered, photographed, and subjected to detailed analysis.

Inclusion Criteria: All the cadavers used for dissection of undergraduate teaching in the year 2019-2020 obtained from the Department of Anatomy, irrespective of age and sex were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Damaged kidneys due to improper handling during dissection were excluded.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical Analysis using chi-square test was done by using the Epi info software. Chi-square test of significance was applied for association between the occurrence of kidney anomalies and the side of the kidney, considering statistical significance at p-value <0.05.

Results

Out of the 48 specimens, 24% (12 specimen) exhibited renal and ureteric anomalies. Among these, 18% (9 specimen) demonstrated kidney anomalies & 10% (5 specimen) had double ureter with notable cases including:

Specimen 1: It was an unusual variation of horseshoe kidney so we called it as a variant. In this specimen, right kidney was found to be in its normal position while left kidney was moved in the midline and its lower pole was fused with the lower pole of right kidney. The left kidney overlapped the major abdominal vessels i.e. abdominal aorta and inferior vena cava. The inferior mesenteric artery was crossing over the anterior surface of left kidney. The right kidney was found to have double ureter which fused 4cm below the hilum while left kidney also showed double ureter arising from two hila. They fused on the anterior surface of left kidney. The right kidney also had accessory renal artery arising from main renal artery. It runs above main renal artery and pierces the substance of kidney at the hilum. Left kidney shows two hila on its anterior surface with two renal arteries arising from aorta. One renal artery arises from left side of aorta above the origin of inferior mesenteric artery and another renal artery arises from right side of aorta below the origin of inferior mesenteric artery (Fig. 1)

Figure 1: Variant of horseshoe kidney showing bilateral double ureter

Specimen 2: Bilateral polycystic kidneys with large, thin-walled cysts (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Bilateral polycystic kidneys with large, thin-walled cysts

Specimen 3: Bilateral polycystic kidneys with pre-hilar branching of renal arteries and kidney shrinkage .

Figure 3: Bilateral polycystic kidney showing pre-hilar branching of renal artery

Specimen 4: Bilateral double ureter with fusion at different levels on each side. Double ureter on right side fuses at the lower border of L2 while double ureter on left side fuses at the level of L5-S1 intervertebral disc.

Figure 4: Bilateral Double Ureter

Specimen 5: Bilateral lobulated kidneys with accessory renal arteries and variations in polar artery origins. On left side, polar artery was arising from abdominal aorta. On right side, accessory renal artery was seen to be arising from main renal artery.

Figure 5: Bilateral lobulated kidneys with accessory renal arteries

Specimen 6: Unilateral double ureter. (Fig. 6)**Figure 6: Unilateral double ureter.****Specimen 7: Unilateral elongated kidney. (Fig. 7)****Figure 7: Unilateral elongated kidney**

Since, Calculated Chi-square value is 0.2193 is less than the critical value of 3.84, we fail to reject the null hypothesis at the 0.05 significance level. This suggests that, based on the given data, there is not enough evidence to conclude a statistically significant association between the occurrence of anomalies and the side of the kidneys.

Discussion

In this study, the various anomalous findings indicate that renal and ureteral variations are not as

simple as they might appear. These results show how complex embryology, genetics, and environment work [1].

The results of our study pointing to the importance of anatomical investigation on a regional basis. This high prevalence (24%) is consistent with other studies [Table 1] that have shown a significant occurrence of such anomalies in general populations [6,7,8]. Worth noting is the fact that this local prevalence points to possible genetic-environment interplay unique to Nashik.

Such observed patterns of kidney and ureter anomalies make interesting cases in understanding variations in anatomy [Table 2]. Among these patterns, an example of horseshoe kidney “variant” (Specimen 1) could be seen to display how intricate they may be especially because of their vascular overlaps [9]. Also horseshoe kidney has been reported elsewhere. The renal form anomaly can either take structural or fusion types of anomalies. Horse shoe kidney occurs where there is fusion at the midline between two separate functioning kidneys [1,3].

This case illustrates one reason why understanding the nuances of renal variation is important for clinical management and surgical intervention.

Bilateral polycystic kidneys are clinically relevant findings accompanied with major issues in patients' management and they were present both in Specimens 2,3. Polycystic kidney disease, which is a genetic disorder that causes multiple cysts to grow in the kidneys [10]. Adult polycystic kidney disease (ADPKD) is an autosomal dominant disease with high penetrance caused by mutations in one of the two genes, PKD1 and PKD2. Failure of the ureteric bud to integrate and branch appropriately into the metanephros during development of kidney resulted in multiple cystic disease of kidney [2,3]

Accessory renal arteries (Specimen 5) show the complex vascular network that provides blood to the kidney and challenges resulting from this variability with surgical procedures [9].

The discovery of unilateral and bilateral double ureters (Specimens 4 & 6) highlights the complexity which characterizes urinary tract development, as well its relevance for a broader understanding of renal-collecting-system morphology in clinical

practice [11,12,13]. Anomalies such as unilateral elongated kidney (Specimen 7) highlight the variability of normal anatomical structures that can affect clinical impressions [14,15,16]

In our study, the observed distribution of kidney anomalies between the right and left kidneys is not statistically significant at the chosen significance level. The difference in the occurrence of kidney anomalies between the right and left kidneys could likely be due to random variation rather than a meaningful pattern or association.

Our findings at the forefront of anatomical studies and clinical application underline the indispensable role of anatomical knowledge in a medical practitioner's repertoire. The present variations reported add to the fast-growing database of anatomy, furthering our knowledge on regional anatomical variation and thus enriching medical education, research, and service to patients.

This study, therefore, represents the first formal documentation of the prevalence, patterns, and peculiar features of kidney and ureter anomalies among cadavers in the Nashik region of Maharashtra, India. The findings observed are immensely useful to clinicians, field researchers, and academicians working in this area.

Our study brings to light the different kinds of kidney and ureter anomalies in Nashik District, drawing out a rich tapestry of human anatomical variations. Our findings, compared with other anatomical and clinical literature, provide important clues towards the understanding of local prevalence and trends of these anomalies. The list of references cited in our study adds strength to the findings and correlates our observations with prevailing knowledge in anatomy.

Table 1: Comparison of Prevalence of Kidney and Ureter Anomalies in Various Studies

Study	Region/Population	Sample Size	Prevalence (%)
Present Study	Nashik, Maharashtra, India	48	25
Shambharkar et al., 2018	Mumbai, Maharashtra, India	99	27.27
Kasat et al., 2018	Mumbai, Maharashtra, India	180	23.3
Choudhary et al., 2017	Uttar Pradesh, India	64	12.5

Table 2: Comparison of Types of Kidney and Ureter Anomalies Among Various Studies

Anomaly Type	Present Study	Shambharkar et al., 2018	Kasat et al., 2018	Choudhary et al., 2017
Polycystic Kidney	Yes	Yes	No	No
Horseshoe Kidney	Yes	No	No	No
Double Ureter	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Lobulated Kidney	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Accessory Renal Artery	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive insight into the prevalence, patterns, and distinct characteristics of kidney and ureter anomalies among cadavers from

the Nashik region. The documented variations, including polycystic kidneys, lobulated kidneys, and a variant of horseshoe kidney, underscore the importance of regional anatomical studies in

enhancing our understanding of anatomical diversity. These findings have implications for clinical diagnosis, surgical planning, and personalized patient care.

References:

1. Abdallah P. H, Cassia T. S, Marcelo S. T, Gustavo P. R, Taísa P. D, Roberto B, and Fernanda G. V. Congenital Anomalies of the Upper Urinary Tract: A Comprehensive Review. *RadioGraphics* 2021;41(2): 462-486. <https://doi.org/10.1148/rg.2021200078>
2. Campbell MF, Walsh PC: *Campbell's urology. Anomalies of the Upper Urinary Tract.* Walsh PC, Retik AB, Vaughan ED Jr, Wein AJ (ed): WB Saunders, Philadelphia; 1992. 2:1376-1381.
3. Sadler TW: *Langman's Medical Embryology.* Sadler TW (ed): Wolters Kluwer, Philadelphia; 2018.
4. Standring S, eds. *Gray's anatomy: The anatomical basis of clinical practice.* 41st ed. Edinburgh: Elsevier 2016
5. Koshi R. The abdomen. In: *Cunningham's Manual of Practical Anatomy, 16th Edition, Vol 2,* New York: Oxford University Press. 2017:190-92.
6. Kasat P, Bhosale Y, Muthiyani G: A cadaveric study of variations in the urological system . *Int J Anat Res.* 2018, 6:5686-5694. <https://doi.org/10.16965/ijar.2018.311>
7. Shweta B Shambharkar, Shabana Borate, Suresh Gangane. A Human Cadaveric Study on Incidence and Morphology of Anatomical Variations of Kidney and Ureter with Emphasis on its Embryological, Genetic and Clinical Significance. *Int J Anat Res* 2018;6 (4.2):5892-5910. <https://doi.org/10.16965/ijar.2018.370>
8. Choudhary U, Kumar S, Jee K, Singh A, Bharti P: A cadaveric study on anatomical variations of kidney and ureter in India. *Int J Res Med Sci.* 2017, 5:2358. 10.18203/2320-6012.
9. Anturlikar V, Moolya P, Bhusari P, Satpute S, Patil D. A Cadaveric Study of Variations of Renal Artery from Nashik, Maharashtra, India. *Journal of Clinical & Diagnostic Research.* 2022 Dec 1;16(12).
10. Granthem, J.J., Nair V, Winklhofer F. Cystic diseases of the kidney. In: Brenner BM, ed. *Brenner and Rector's The Kidney.* Vol. 26 th ed. Philadelphia: WB Saunders Company; 2000 pp.1699-1730.
11. Dorko F, Tokarcik J, Vyborna E: Congenital malformations of the ureter: anatomical studies . *Anat Sci Int.* 2015, 91:290-294.
12. Saxena A. K., Saxena A. (2004). Rare congenital anomalies of the kidneys, urinary tract, and genitalia: An autopsy study. *Pediatric Surgery International,* 20(11-12), 855-858.
13. Neuman M, Eidelman A, Langer R, Golan A, Bukovsky I, Caspi E: Iatrogenic injuries to the ureter during gynecologic and obstetric operations. *Surg Gynec Obstet.* 1991, 173:268-272.
14. Deka B, Saikia R: A study of human cadaveric ureter by simple dissection method. *Int J Anat Res.* 2016, 4:3005-3008.
15. Roy M, Singh BR, Gajbe UL, Thute P: Anatomical variations of ureter in central India: a cadaveric study. *J Datta Meghe Inst Med Sci Univ.* 2017, 12:277-279.
16. Prakash, Rajini T, Venkatiah J, Bhardwaj AK, Singh DK, Singh G: Double ureter and duplex system: a cadaver and radiological study. *Urol J.* 2011, 8:145-148.